

http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```
Search<!-- Use /re/ syntax for regexp search -->
1 <html lang="pt-PT">
2
3
4 <head>
5     <meta charset="UTF-8">
6     <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
7     <link rel="profile" href="http://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9     <title>Marketing Digital Tools &#8211; Agência de Mar
10 <link rel="dns-prefetch" href="//s.w.org" />
11 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
12 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
13 <script type="text/javascript">
14     window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl": "https://s.
15     !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("ca
16 </script>
17 <style type="text/css">
18 img.wp-smiley,
19 img.emoji {
20     display: inline !important;
21     border: none !important;
22     box-shadow: none !important;
23     height: 1em !important;
24     width: 1em !important;
25     margin: 0 .07em !important;
26     vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
27     background: none !important;
28     padding: 0 !important;
29 }
30 </style>
31 <link rel="stylesheet" id="wp-block-library-css" href="ht
32 <link rel="stylesheet" id="wc-block-style-css" href="http://g
33 <link rel="stylesheet" id="dashicons-css" href="http://plugi
34 <link rel="stylesheet" id="everest-forms-general-css" href="h
35 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-layout-css" href="http:
36 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-small-screen-css" href=
37 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-general-css" href="htt
38 <style id="woocommerce-inline-inline-css" type="text/css">
39 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
40 </style>
41 <link rel="stylesheet" id="font-awesome-css" href="http://plu
42 <link rel="stylesheet" id="zakra-style-css" href="http://plug
43 <style id="zakra-style-inline-css" type="text/css">
44 @media (min-width: 1200px) { .tg-container{max-width: 1200px;}
45 .tg-primary-menu > div ul li a{font-family: -apple-system, bli
46 </style>
47 <link rel="stylesheet" id="zakra-woocommerce-style-css" href=
48 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-icons-css" href="http://
49 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-animations-css" href="ht
50 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-frontend-css" href="http:
51 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-global-css" href="http://
52 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-post-24-css" href="http:
53 <link rel="stylesheet" id="google-fonts-1-css" href="https://
54 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-icons-shared-0-css" href=
55 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-icons-fa-solid-css" href=
56 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-icons-fa-brands-css" href=
57 <script type="text/javascript" src="http://plugin53.marketing
58 <script type="text/javascript" src="http://plugin53.marketing
59 <link rel="https://api.w.org/" href="http://plugin53.marketing
60 <link rel="EditURI" type="application/rsd+xml" title="RSD" href=
61 <link rel="wlwmanifest" type="application/wlwmanifest+xml" href=
62 <meta name="generator" content="WordPress 5.3.2" />
63 <meta name="generator" content="Everest Forms 1.5.10" />
64 <meta name="generator" content="WooCommerce 3.9.1" />
65 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin53.marketingdigitalto
66 <link rel="shortlink" href="http://plugin53.marketingdigitalto
67 <link rel="alternate" type="application/json+oembed" href="ht
68 <link rel="alternate" type="text/xml+oembed" href="http://
69 <!-- Markup (JSON-LD) structured in schema.org ver.4.7.0 S
70 <script type="application/ld+json">
```

Detetado BlogPosting 0 ERROS (1) 0 AVISOS 7 ITENS

BlogPosting	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
@type	BlogPosting				
headline	marketingdigitaltools.com				
datePublished	2019-02-02T15:11:19+00:00				
dateModified	2020-02-04T12:22:30+00:00				
mainEntityOfPage	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM		
@type	WebPage				
url	http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.com/				
name	http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.com/				
author	0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 1 ITEM				
@type	Person				
name	sarjuliao				
image	0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 1 ITEM				
@type	ImageObject				
url	http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/PLANO-MKT-VISIBILIDADE-150x150.png				
width	150				
height	150				
publisher	0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 1 ITEM				
@type	Organization				
name	Marketing Digital Tools				
logo	0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 1 ITEM				
@type	ImageObject				
url	http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-Slogan.png				
width	463				
height	330				
speakeable	0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 1 ITEM				
@type	SpeakableSpecification				
cssSelector	Em 2025 mais de 85% dos internautas portugueses farão compras online				
cssSelector	Prepare já a sua empresa para começar a vender online! As compras online são cada vez mais parte integrante dos internautas por todo o mundo. Cómodo, sem filas de espera e a partir de qualquer dispositivo com ligação à internet, estes são apenas alguns dos fatores chaves na decisão para a adoção e crescimento acelerado destes [...]				